

Cancer detection by machine learning

Md Haris Uddin Sharif¹

University of the Cumberland, Williamsburg, Kentucky, USA

Abstract— Cancer is a terminal condition, often caused by the aggregation of genetic defects and several disease modifications. Cancer cells are pathological regions that are often life-threatening in some portion of the human body. At the early stage, cancer, also known as the tumor, must be diagnosed easily and properly to determine what may potentially treat it. However, modalities are different, such as complicated history, inaccurate diagnostics and care, which are the major causes of death. The study aims to review, assess, classify, and discuss existing advances to diagnose human body cancer by breast, brain, lung, liver, skin cancer, and leukemia machine learning methods. The research demonstrates how machine learning with supervised, unmonitored, and deep learning approaches helps cancer diagnosis and the curing process. Various state-of-the-art methods are classified under the same class, and outcomes from precision, sensitivity, specificity, and false positives metrics. Metrics are compared on benchmark data sets. In conclusion, obstacles for potential future work are also outlined.

Index Terms—Artificial Intelligence, Biomedical Image Analysis, Cancer diagnosis, Deep neural network, Machine Learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

Medical imaging research plays a vital part in identifying various parts of the body, such as blood cancer, skin cancer, breast cancer, brain tumor, lung cancer, and retina. GLOBOCAN estimates reveal that in 2018, about 18.1 million new cancer cases resulted in 9.6 million deaths from cancer [06]. The study reveals that lung cancer is the most important source of expiration (18.4%), followed by breast cancer (6.6%), colon (5.8%) prostate cancer (3.8%), and skin cancer, including melanoma and not melanoma (1.3 per cent) [06].

In the human body, the brain is the most essential and complex organ. Inappropriate mitosis pathways control the conduct of morphological cells in the human brain. Cancerous cells with many morphological features, example size and strength, have been developed during this process. There are two main types of brain tumor, called low and high rates. A low-grade tumor is rising steadily, whereas the high grade is violent and disturbs the brain's blood flow. Many malignant brain tumors are also known as neuroepithelial tumors. The percentage of such brain cancers to 5 per cent and patients' survival time is less than five years. The bulk of cancer cells have a poor comparison with surrounding cells. Glioblastoma is a frequent type of tumor. Accurate diagnosis of brain tumors is also critical. A painless technique, which provides aid in studying tumors from various viewpoints, was primarily used

for brain tumor diagnosis. The main way of identifying brain tumors, for instance, is the study of MR pictures.

A pulmonary nodule may be a cancer symptom in the lungs. Pulmonary cancer is a fatal illness that requires early diagnosis to preserve patients' lives. An item with a circular forming is a benign or malignant nodule. The malignant nodule is rapidly developing, and malignant nodules will also rapidly develop in the other organ. It is essential to treat malignant nodules in the initial stage for this reason. The diagnostics of lung cancer is the most commonly used CT scan. Following a CT scan, more study is required if abnormal lung areas are to be found.

The dominant cause of death for women is breast cancer. Significant cancer patients above the age of 50 are observed. In 2017, nearly 40.610 females expired because of breast cancer in the US, according to Meenalochini et.al, Malignant and benign can occur in the breast with two groups of abnormal cells. Malignant cells are cancer cells that, when replicated or meta-situated in other bodies, are more harmful. Both benign and large cells are formed, although the number of malignant cells is very limited. Due to the disadvantages of fatty and dense tissue size and incidence, malignant tumors at the beginning of the cycle are exceedingly difficult to detect. Advanced auto- or computerized devices often need to classify the tumor end of the breast.

Cancer of the skin is one of the most common diseases around the globe. Uncontrolled formation of abnormal cells in the skin forms a skin cancer. There are two forms of skin cancer, melanom and melanomanon-a are found. Melanoma is harmful rather than non-melanoma, a severe form of tumor or cancer that starts from the skin and appears like a dark spot. They often go from a mole to develop in size, uneven margins, itchiness, skin disintegration and color. In 2018 there were 9,320 deaths of 3330 women and 5990 men due to skin cancer (S., 2020). Melanoma percentage is the highest and smaller in Asia, Latin America and Africa in North America, Europe, Australia and New Zealand. The report states that the mortality rate will decline by up to 90 percent of skin cancer is diagnosed early (S., 2020).. This indicates that early diagnosis of cancer is crucial because it can reduce the associated risk factor.

Acute lymphocytic Leukemia or Acute Lymphocytic Leukemia is the type of cancer attributed to immature lymphocytes in the bone marrow (ALL). Leukaemia is rapidly developing and migrates to various parts of the body, including spleen, liver, lymph nodes, brain and nervous systems. Both of the blood and bone marrow affect. Leukaemia in healthy children is the majority in children, but

recurring Leukemia and Myeloid Leukemia in babies are uncommon. The malignancy in leukaemia cell growth and progeny have been generalized to complex molecular approaches [02]. This is known as Leukemia for hematogenic cell development. Acute Leukemia induces more than 20 per cent of explosions in the bone marrow (S., 2020).

The liver is a fundamental part of the human body that fulfils basic functions, such as drug detoxification, the development of blood proteins, and the filtering of the blood from waste components. In place of this, an illness in the human body is highly important, particularly if a cancer diagnosis has been made. Liver cancer is commonly known as hepatic cancer which is the most serious and aggressive ailment. The most prevalent form of liver cancer, causing up to 80 per cent of death has been Hepatocellular Carcinoma (HCC) (S., 2020).. GLOBOCAN estimates that liver cancer is the world's 6th and 7th leading cause of deaths among both men and women.

In my discussion, having a variety of cancers, I shall now focus on two types of cancers to showcase how machine learning assists in detecting these diseases.

II. SCOPE AND OBJECTIVES

A. Scope and Objectives

A new field of early-detection research on cancer has been opened up by different forms of cancer detection and classification using the computer assistance that has shown the potential to eliminate manual system impairments. The present survey provides numerous sections on the cutting-edge methods, analysis and comparisons for F-measurement, sensitiveness, precision, precise, and accurate data sets for brain tumours, breast cancer, prostate cancer, liver tumours and Leukemia, and skin lesion identification. This diagram provides a pictorial example of this analysis.

B. Benchmark Datasets

The section discusses data sets commonly used to experiment, analyze, and compare state-of-the-art technologies' cancer tests and rankings. The section also highlights their source, training sets, test sets, cancer detection success metrics, segmentation and classification.

C. Brats 2015 Datasets

This dataset consists of 274 sets, of 192 training cases (154 HGG and 38 LGG), 82 test cases and 82 trials cases from the Perelman School of the University of Medicine in Pennsylvania (66 HGG and 16 LGG [08]. The training pictures include high quality and low glioma with ground-level reality. The ground trueness is noted in five codes, for example, 1 for necrosis, 2 for edema, 3 for tumor-free improvement, 4 for tumor enhancement, and 0 for everything else.

D. Brain Tumor

A brain tumor is an irregular four-degree cell array. Brain tumors in grade 1 and 2 appear to develop slowly, and cancers in grades 3 and 4 grow rapidly and difficult to treat. Tumors of

grade 2 are malignant and cancerous. The pre-processing procedure is carried out to eliminate the sound and non-brain tissue from image input for greater precision. There are several primary steps for tumor identification. The techniques BSE (brain surface extraction) are used to eliminate non-brain organ. The simple non-local mean (FNLN), partial differential diffusion (PDDF) and Wiener filter are used for noise reduction and contrast depletion for better contrast. Fuzzy Cmean, k-mean and Otsu threshold approaches are the most common brain tumor segmentation techniques. In the same way, Net architecture is also one of the popular CNN architectures for brain cancer segmentation.

Hand-crafted features are collected after the segmentation process to turn the fractured images into math explanations. More rigorous methods are currently employed to isolate features and then to identify them. The most popular techniques for extraction include histogram orientation gradient (HOG), Gabor wavelet transform (GWT), local binary patterns (LBP), and form-based functions. Also, multiple filtering and reduction methods are used for maximizing function selection, such as a genetic algorithm (GA) and the main component analysis (PCA). At present, CNN architecture is often known as an effective tool for the diagnosis of brain tumours.

Fig: 01 [10].

To increase image transparency, multiple variations are created. The preprocessing methods, including noise, complement optimal performance changes, decreasing, equalizing histograms, and enhancing tip. In the latest model's class, the weighting is used to deal with the topic of class disparity. Details of validation are inspected in a learned model from the same image set, and each experiment's results are reported. ConvNet, as one score (accuracy) of 75% and 80% of the total fusion of 82.29% is provided by an LSTM-based network [08]. The defined model is validated by the MICCAI Challenge database, including multi-modal brain tumor segmentation (BRATS) 2015, 2016 and 2017, respectively, using the latest science imaging and computer-assisted intervention [08]. Such technologies are developed by entropy to quickly and accurately detect and interact with fused vectors to classification units. The study results were 0.99 with 2015 BRATS, 1.00 with 2016 BRATS and 0.99 with 2017 BRATS with a coefficient of dice similarity (DSC) [08]. They did not, though, use other classifiers or their fusion to check their technique's feasibility.

E. Lung Cancer

Lung disease is a major cause of lung death worldwide. Several patients will benefit from operative, percutaneous and operational therapies in the case of a thin, diffuse tumor. Unfortunately, since few patients show no symptoms in the early stages of infection, 75 percent of lung cancers will be diagnosed later in a gradual pathological state, nodal and metastatic disease [01]. According to studies in Australia, the average survivability level of patients with lung cancer is about 15% [01]. Multiple authors have documented their work with the LIDC/IDRI database in the field of pulmonary nodule identification and classification.

Using machine learning approaches helps detect and evaluate pulmonary nodules by using artificial intelligence tools to analyze CT images. These systems are referred to as decision support systems, which evaluate the images using the preprocessing, segmentation, extraction, and classification.

MCNN is used to capture nodular heterogeneity by separating discriminatory features from alternative layers. MCNN is used to capture nodular. Lung nodule scanning and annotation was used to test the proposed LIDC-IDRI process. There are three CNNs in this system in the MCNN model, which assemble input parallel nodule patches of different sizes. The segmentation process is 97 per cent and is based on the LIDC database [01].

Effective pulmonary nodular detection based on several patches from the lung picture of the Frangi filter. A 4-channel neural network model gathers input from radiologists to classify nodules from four layers through the combination of two picture groups. 80.06 percent of the sensitivity could be achieved with 4.7 false positives for each scan and a 15.1 false-positive sensitivity per sample [01]. They concluded that in multiple classes, the patch-based learning approach increases efficiency and significantly decreases false positives in a large number of image data [02].

Finally, a deep thought approach based on the stored autoencoder and SoftMax was applied to those false-positive results. The partnerships between Lung Image Database and the Image Database Network Initiative, the largest publicly available database, indicate that the proposed approach lowered false by 2.8 per scan significantly with an opportunity for 95.6percent sensitivities [01].

A modern 3D nodule processing hybrid sensor, including the Active Contour Model (ACM) and the networking of 3D neighborhood based on the spatial characteristics in the next step. Combining geometrical texture with the (PCA) in each candidate Nodule, the Theory Component Analysis produces a hybrid functions vector (HOG-PCA). The triage is performed using four distinct grade models, namely Naive Bayesian, SVM and Adaboost. After the abstraction process, four different classifications are added. A sample of the Lungs Image Consortium is used for the assessment (LIDC) [09].

III. CHALLENGES

The main obstacles for cancer diagnosis and the curing process are the redesign of a cancer testing pipeline, the

understanding of cancer growth hypothesis, the creation of preclinical models for the treatment of difficult tumors, early treatment and innovative approaches for planning and carrying out clinical studies [05]. The need for huge data sets, which may not be available for cancer tissues, is a drawback of deep learning approaches. This model can boost efficiency and expose more valuable trends as more gene expression data become available. Machine learning algorithms can also be very scalable to big data inputs [03]. Due to the high dimensionality and sophistication of these results, cancer prediction continues to present a challenge. Despite decades of research, the clinical diagnosis of cancer and tumor-specific marker recognition are still elusive [04].

IV. EXPERIMENT

At a stage where the cancer is known in a patient, laboratory tests are performed. A blood sample is typically taken for blood count testing. Determination of signs of cancer is helpful for many cancers. Depending on the cancer presence in the blood, the number of tumor markers vary. In cancer screening, tracking and pronostic assessment, tumor markers may be used. A blood examination may assess the occurrence of the markers. Tumor markers are secreted into the blood from the tumor tissue. The detection or accumulation of tumor markers may signal the progression or recurrence of cancer.

V. CONCLUSION

In recent decades, computer service has seen a breakthrough in cancer diagnosis and treatment. However, this paper has submitted a thorough assessment of current diagnostic and curative methods for various cancers that seriously damage the human body. This article focuses on evaluating, examining, categorizing, and defining various types of cancer methodologies but focused deeply on brain and lung cancer to showcase how machine learning assists in cancer detection. Future study of multiple cancer types is important to identify biomarkers for cancer-specific applications. Furthermore, the study of aggregated heterogeneous cancer data may contribute to the identification of cross-cancer biomarkers.

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